

HadISDH.extremes Homogeneity Score Document

Kate Willett

23rd May 2023

Inhomogeneity is ubiquitous in weather station data given the many historical changes made to instruments, their housing, their location and surrounding environments and also the various methodological practices for observing, recording and reporting. While such changes can be detected and adjusted for this is complex for daily and especially sub-daily data with a high risk of 'doing more harm' given the large variability at these scales.

HadISDH.extremes data have not been homogenised because they are based on a single value for each day which means that they are highly variable. Instead, inhomogeneity information from the sister product HadISDH.land(T and Tw) is used to assign a score for each gridbox month in HadISDH.extremes. The HadISDH.land station records have been homogenised at the monthly mean level. Where an inhomogeneity is detected the station series is adjusted accordingly and the size of the adjustment stored for each month. When the HadISDH.extremes station month indices are gridded the HadISDH.land station month adjustment size is passed through and used to create a set of 8 scores for each gridbox as described in Table 1.

These HQ scores (hq1 to hq8) combine the number of stations contributing to the gridbox month in question and the size of any adjustments made to any of those stations during that month. Scores are higher where there are fewer stations and / or larger adjustments as this shows that the gridbox month is affected by inhomogeneity to a larger extent. The HQ Flag (hqscore) is a sum of HQ1 to HQ8 and can be used to make decisions on whether to keep or discard a gridbox month. When excluding gridbox months based on their HQ Flag there will be a trade off between data completeness and data quality. We recommend that excluding gridbox months with an HQ Flag > 6 is a good balance.

Table 1. Homogeneity quality (HQ) scoring system. All scores are applied at the individual gridbox month level. Red text indicates critical scores where gridbox months are of extremely poor quality and exclusion is recommended. (replicated from Willett, 2023: Willett, K, in press: HadISDH.extremes Part 1: a gridded wet bulb temperature extremes index product for climate monitoring. Advances in Atmospheric Sciences, doi: 10.1007/s00376-023-2347-8.

<http://www.iapjournals.ac.cn/aas/en/article/doi/10.1007/s00376-023-2347-8>.)

Homogeneity Variable	Description	Scoring Detail	Worst Case
HQ 1: Station Count	Number of stations	1 station = 1, > 1 stations = 0	1 station only, moderate quality
HQ 2: Inhomogeneity Density	Ratio of HadISDH.land inhomogeneity adjustments present per station: count of stations with adjustment present divided by total count of stations	1 per station = 2, 0-1 per station = 1, 0 per station = 0	1 per station, poor quality
HQ 3: Small Inhomogeneity Density	Ratio of 0-0.5 ° C inhomogeneity adjustments present per station: count of stations with > 0 ° C and <	1 per station = 1, 0-1 per station = 0, 0 per station = 0	1 per station, moderate quality

HQ 4: Moderate Inhomogeneity Density	0.5 ° C absolute adjustment present divided by total count of stations Ratio of 0.5-1 ° C inhomogeneity adjustments present per station: count of stations with ≥ 0.5 ° C and < 1 ° C absolute adjustment present divided by total count of stations	1 per station = 3 , 0-1 per station = 1-2 (scaled linearly), 0 per station = 0	1 per station, poor quality
HQ 5: Large Inhomogeneity Density	Ratio of 1-2 ° C inhomogeneity adjustments present per station: count of stations with ≥ 1 ° C and < 2 ° C absolute adjustment present divided by total count of stations	1 per station = 5 , 0-1 per station = 1-4 (scaled linearly), 0 per station = 0	1 per station, very poor quality
HQ 6: Very Large Inhomogeneity Density	Ratio of > 2 ° C inhomogeneity adjustments present per station: count of stations with > 2 ° C absolute adjustment present divided by total count of stations	1 per station = 10 , 0-1 per station = 1-9 (scaled linearly), 0 per station = 0	1 per station, extremely poor quality, exclusion recommended
HQ 7: Mean Adjustment Magnitude	Mean adjustment per station: sum of adjustments present divided by total number of stations	$\geq \pm 2$ ° C = 10 , $\geq \pm 1$ ° C $< \pm 2$ ° C = 4-9 (scaled linearly), $\geq \pm 0.5$ ° C $< \pm 1$ ° C = 2-3 (scaled linearly), $\geq \pm 0$ ° C $< \pm 0.5$ ° C = 1, 0 ° C = 0	$\geq \pm 2$ ° C, extremely poor quality, exclusion recommended
HQ 8: Mean Absolute Adjustment Magnitude	Mean absolute adjustment per station: sum of absolute adjustments present divided by total number of stations	No score. Value is an extra indicator of poor quality.	Not applicable.
HQ Flag	Homogenisation Quality Flag: sum of HQ 1:7	≥ 10 = very poor quality , 7-9 = poor quality, 5-6 = moderate quality, 1-4 = good quality, 0 = excellent quality	≥ 7 , very poor quality or worse, exclusion recommended.
